

CUSTOMERISATION OF BANKING SERVICES IN INDIA

Dr. Divya Nigam,

Assistant Professor, Department of Economics,

Lala Lajpatrai College of Commerce & Economics, Mahalaxmi, Mumbai

Abstract:

Biggest problem plaguing organizations across the globe in bruising and discontinuous environment unleashed by policy of liberalization and globalization by governments around the world is how to cope with rapidly changing business milieu and complex competitive challenges so as to ensure their sustained success. In such an environment being better or bigger is not good enough.

In fiercely competitive environment, a bank, being service organization, needs to be resilient to constantly seek how the environment is changing and how things could be different tomorrow. It must be capable to reinvent business models and redefine its core businesses faster than change in circumstances so that it achieves superior performance and provides products/services that customers will pay more than what it costs. Therefore, a bank must have distinct competence to create value.

In its endeavor to create value for the bank, central management needs to undertake value chain analysis of all primary activities which the bank performs such as design and development of product/services, marketing and distribution along with support activities such as technology development, human resource management and infrastructure so as to make their services cost effective, prompt in delivery and customer oriented. The objective of the paper is to find out to what extent the banking sector of India has been successful in customerising the banking services in the last few years and have managed enhance their competitiveness along with meeting the expectations of the banking customers.

Key words; *Customerising, Relationship Banking, Banking Ombudsman, Relationship management.*

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Introduction:

In market driven economy, individual customers are like king, who are well connected and informed through 'Net' and who have power to pick and choose and put together their solutions, depending upon their level of sophistication, knowledge and skills, cannot be expected to accept products/ services offered by the bank.

Under the circumstances, the management is left with no option but to co-opt customers' experiences in value creation activities. It has to develop systems and services through collaboration with customers to generate value for the bank and its customers with a view to unlocking value creation opportunities and exploiting them.

The above exercise of value creation and recreation should be done continually in the light of dynamically changing environment, and growing sophistication of customers demanding better service and higher value and aspiring for personal care and, craft the strategy accordingly. This will aid the bank to retain and enhance the existing value in future.

Objectives of the study:

- a. To analyze the present state of bank customer relationship management.
- b. To present various guidelines of Reserve Bank to be complied by banks for promoting the customer friendly services.
- c. To assess the response and initiatives taken by Indian banks for achieving customerisation of its services and to evaluate the same.

Research Methodology

The present study is basically analytical in nature, based on the secondary sources of information drawn from the journals, newspaper clippings, periodicals, speeches, RBI reports and circulars and various websites on internet. Period of study taken is 2017-2020.

Backdrop

In competitive market, costs involved in gaining new customers are much higher than those servicing the existing ones and there is a possibility of losing a customer more than a single sale. Under the circumstances, a banks must accord overwhelming focus on providing quality customer service.

Kernel of quality customer service is building relationship banking that involves creating, maintaining and enhancing strong relationships with all types of its customers. This calls for adoption of customer centric strategic approach which seeks to touch all areas and functions of the bank business connected with its value creation and delivery chain. Bank

management must remember that for superb and superior performance on sustained basis, a bank needs enthusiastic customers. Customers can be enthused and enthralled if their feelings, emotions, ideas, actions and connections are duly taken care of by banks while developing and marketing their products/services.

It is most intriguing that relationship banking does not exist in banking industry in India even today in letter and spirit. Whatever facilities banks are providing to their customers in the name of customer service are the outcome of intervention by Reserve Bank of India (RBI). Sensing lukewarm response of the banks to financial sector reforms around the globe and concomitant developments in the banking industry as also apathy of the bank management towards customers, RBI decided to issue policy guidelines way back in 2004 urging the central management of banks to dispense banking services to common person. In the recent years RBI adopted the approach to customer services by empowering the common person in availing banking services and strengthening customer service delivery in banks through a consultative process with bank.

Guidelines of Reserve Bank of India:

- a. Improvement of counter services where in employees to be present at bank counters to deliver the uninterrupted services to the customers preventing long queues.
- b. Display of time norms for certain business transactions
- c. Extension of business hours for non-cash transactions both voucher generating and non-voucher generating transactions (issue of passbook, statement of accounts, issue of cheque book, delivery of term deposit receipts, acceptance of share application form, acceptance of clearing bills/cheques, issue of TDRs, issue of gift cheques, travelers cheques etc.
- d. Provision of note counting machines on the counters
- e. Advisory services on deposit schemes
- f. Safe Deposit lockers
- g. Customer service audit
- h. Customer education with regards to rights and responsibilities in dealing with banks
- i. Fair practice code
- j. Services rendered free of charge
- k. Electronic products like RTGS, NEFT, and ECS etc.
- l. ATM and POS transactions

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- m. Directing banks to inform customers upfront about the requirement of minimum balances and the charges, if such balances are not maintained, provide a choice of a ‘no frills account’ where the minimum balance is nil or very small but having restrictions on number of withdrawals, etc.
 - n. facilitate common man’s access to bank accounts, collection of cheques, provide the drop box facility, credit card operations, nomination facility
 - o. Banks have been directed to introduce ‘Banking Ombudsman’ scheme to redress customer complaints speedily and to provide other facilities pertaining to customer service.
 - p. RBI directed the banks to build adequate institutional machinery for formulating policies and executing them to the benefit of customers.

Response of the Indian Banks to the guidelines of RBI

At the instance of RBI, most Indian banks took measures to render facilities to their customers, such as multiple delivery channels, like ATM, Mobile Banking, Net Banking, Real time gross settlement, Electronic funds transfer, Electronic clearing service, Telebanking, Smart cards, POS devices and initiatives like availability of passbook, printing machines to enable customers to update their passbooks themselves, extended banking hours, management of customer complaints, and introduction of saving and lending schemes from time to time to suit needs especially of high profile customers.

Nevertheless, the above facilities have improved customer services, experience shows that customers’ interests are not always accorded priority. More importantly, concerns have been raised with regard to banking practices that tend to exclude vast segments of the population. It is discombobulating to observe that Indian banks have yet not been able to create enthusiastic customers because of the absence of pleasant ambience and human touch and warmth in dealings by the branch level staff. The customers do not feel being cared by the bank functionaries. Co-opting customers’ experiences by banks in product development and marketing hardly exist. This can be substantiated with the below data showing the complaints and grievances of the customers the recent years.

Category-wise distribution and share of complaints

Failure to meet commitments	11,044	13,332	25,036
	6.75%	6.81%	8.11%
Levy of charges without prior notice	8,209	8,391	18,558

	5.02%	4.28%	6.01%
Loans and advances	6,226	7,610	16,437
	3.81%	3.88%	5.33%
Non-adherence to BCSBI Codes	3,962	5,981	14,194
	2.42%	3.05%	4.60%
Deposit Accounts related	6,719	10,844	8,778
	4.11%	5.54%	2.84%
Pension payments	7,833	7,066	6,307
	4.79%	3.61%	2.04%
Remittances	3,330	3,451	4,045
	2.04%	1.76%	1.31%
DSAs and recovery agents	554	629	1,406
	0.34%	0.32%	0.46%
Para banking	579	1,115	1,117
	0.35%	0.57%	0.36%
Notes and Coins	1,282	480	514
	0.78%	0.25%	0.17%
Others	26,219	28,330	29,204
	16.03%	14.46%	9.46%
Out of purview of BOS	5,681	6,508	8,996
	3.47%	3.32%	2.91%
Total	1,63,590	1,95,901	3,08,630

Note: Figures in % indicate the percentage to total complaints of the respective year

Break-up of ATM/ Debit Card Complaints

Sub-Category	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
Non-payment of cash / account debitedbut cash not dispensed by ATMs	14,691	19,366	31,832
	8.98%	9.89%	10.31%

Debit in account without use of the card or details of the card	2,356	4,481	15,752
	1.44%	2.29%	5.10%
Use of stolen / cloned cards	2117	4,961	7,511
	1.29%	2.53%	2.43%
Account debited more than once for one withdrawal in ATMs or for POS transaction	965	1,288	2,687
	0.59%	0.66%	0.87%
Short payment of cash / less or excess amount of cash dispensed by ATMs	1,166	1,186	1,613
	0.71%	0.61%	0.52%
Others	3,377	5,257	8,405
	2.06%	2.68%	2.72%
Sub-total	24,672	36,539	67,800
	15.08%	18.65%	21.97%
Total complaints received	1,63,590	1,95,901	3,08,630

Note: Figures in % indicate percentage to total number of complaints of respective year

Source: Banking Ombudsman Annual Report -2019-20

Analysis of the data

- i. Slight decline in addressing of customers complaints was witnessed in 2019-20 compared to 2018-19 from 94.03% to 92.36% primary reason being rise in complaints with no corresponding increase in the manpower.
- ii. Share of customer's complaints regarding ATM/ Debit Cards, Mobile/ Electronic banking exceeded those pertaining to non-observance of Fair Practices Code (FPC) as the major grounds of complaints during the year 2019-20.
- iii. There has been increase in complaints regarding credit cards, failure to meet commitments, levy of charges without notice, loans and advances and non-adherence to the Banking Codes and Standards Board of India (BCSBI) Codes during 2019-20 compared to the previous year.

Suggestions:

It must be noted that no amount of consultations and product offerings and technological sophistication are going to attract new customers and retain the existing ones if the bank

functionaries do not create pleasant and powerful customers experiences and their emotions and feelings are not deeply respected every time.

Thus, nucleus of Indian banking success in ferociously competitive environment is building deeper banking relationship with customers. For this, top management need to foster relationship with customers as one of the bank's principal objective that will guide formulation of relationship strategy to bind all the elements toward customer service.

Creating customer centric organizational culture, where every bank employee has to be a part of process leading to customer satisfaction, is necessary for successful relationship. Thus, a realization of each employee's basic role towards customers' satisfaction will indubitably strengthen adoption of relationship banking.

Motivating employees at all levels to understand concept and philosophy of relationship banking calls for setting expectations to help individuals and groups align their performance with the goals of relationship banking and reward them accordingly.

To encapsulate, creation of value of a product/service in collaboration with customers has become cliché for organizations including banks around the globe in view of escalating competitive environment and growing sophistication of customers demanding better service and higher value, and aspiring for personal care.

Conclusion

For customerisation of banking services building strong relationship banking with customers is inevitable. This demands adoption of customer centric strategic approach. Unfortunately relationship banking does not exist in Indian banking industry in letter and spirit even today. Of course, banks have begun providing various facilities to customers during the last one and half decade but at the instance of RBI. Time has come when top management has to realize that to survive and thrive in highly competitive market, customers have to be accorded primacy and their experiences and emotions are deeply respected in service offerings. Accordingly, organizational culture needs to be customer-centric and bank employees have to be goaded to strive their best to satisfy their customers.

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